

MSCs Protocol

Info regarding the cells that we received:

- **1 vial of CLI 003** – MSC derived *from bone marrow* (from a healthy volunteer, gift from Timothy O'Brien and Aaron Liew from the Remedy Lab in Ireland) frozen at *passage 4* on 06/11/2013 in 90% SVF + 10% DMSO with about *2.2 million cells per vials*
- **2 vials of FA7** – MSC derived *from adipose tissue* (lipoaspirate from knee and inner thighs of a 29-year-old woman, tested negative for HIV and hepatitis) frozen at *passage 1* on 13/07/2012 in 90% SVF + 10% DMSO with about *1.5 million cells per vial*. They were tested negative for mycoplasma contamination on 10/07/2012
- **1 vial of FA8** – MSC derived *from adipose tissue* (lipoaspirate from knee, hip and, thighs of a 20-year-old woman, tested negative for HIV and hepatitis) frozen at *passage 1* on 13/07/2012 in 90% SVF + 10% DMSO with about *1.5 million cells per vial*. They were tested negative for mycoplasma contamination on 10/07/2012

The vials they sent us are from their master cell bank (passage 1). They will recommend us thaw one vial and expand the cells to make a working cell bank (around passage 5) for future use. Then we can use the cells from this working cell bank up to about passage 10, then, go back to the next vial.

Mesenchymal Stem Cell Culture Medium:

- DMEM High Glucose
- 10% FBS
- 100 U/mL (1%) Penicillin/Streptomycin
- Glutamax

Thawing of cells:

[They recommend thawing the cells at the end of day 0 and to replace the medium with fresh medium first thing in the next morning]

Day 0:

1. Do not thaw the cells until proper media and plasticware are on hand.
2. Remove the vial of mesenchymal stem cells from liquid nitrogen and incubate in a 37°C water bath for the minimum required time until a small ice crystal remains. Maximum cell viability is dependent on the rapid thawing of frozen cells. *Warning: Do not vortex the cells!*
3. As soon as the cells are completely thawed, disinfect the outside of the vial with 70% ethanol.
4. In a laminar flow bio-safety II hood, collect the cells (around 1 mL) with a micropipette using blue pipet tip and transfer it to a sterile 50 mL conical tube. *Warning: Be careful to not introduce any bubbles during the transfer process!*
5. Using a 50 mL pipette, slowly add 49 mL of Mesenchymal Stem Cell Culture Medium (pre-warmed to 37°C) to the 50 mL conical tube (do the first 10 mL dropwise). *Warning: Do not add the whole volume of medium at once to the cells. This may result in decreased cell viability due to osmotic shock!*
6. Gently mix the cell suspension by slow pipetting up and down. *Warning: Be careful to not introduce any bubbles and do not vortex the cells!*
7. Distribute the cells in 2 T175 (25 mL per flask). We usually plate between 1000 and 5000 MSCs per cm². For thawing we usually seed one vial (1.5 to 2.2 million cells) in 2 to 3 T175 (with 25 mL per flask).

Warning: Do not Vortex the cells. This way cryo-preserveative (DMSO) is sufficiently diluted (0.2%) to let the cells for about 12h before changing the medium!

8. Incubate the cells overnight at 37°C in a 5% CO₂ humidified incubator.

Day 1:

9. In the morning change to fresh Mesenchymal Stem Cell Culture Medium (prewarmed to 37°C) and every two to three days thereafter.
10. When the cells are 80-90% confluent, they can be dissociated and subculture or alternatively frozen for later use.

From Day 2:

Replace culture medium every 2-3 days, until reach ~80% confluency.

Warning: Too confluent would induce a transformation!

Sub-culture cells using standard methods of trypsinization using TrypLE Express (Cat. 12604013; ThermoFisher):

- Remove the culture medium
- Wash once with 1x PBS (tempered at 37°C).
- Add 5 to 10 ml of TrypLE 1x (Cat. 12604013; ThermoFisher) per T175 and leave in the incubator at 37°C (3-5 minutes), check under the microscope, and stop when cells get detached (**Warning:** they are hard to detach and usually we tap the bottom of the flask to detach the cells that remain attached!)
- Resuspend the cells in Mesenchymal Stem Cell Culture Medium (45 to 40 mL per T175) and transfer in 2 T175 (25 mL per T175). **Note:** usually we do not centrifuge the cells when we pass them and we do not count them, but some protocols do.

Split the cells when they reach about 80% confluency (not more). Usually, we split them on Monday and Friday weekly at a ratio of 1:3 to 1:2 (depending on their confluency and observed growth rate). This corresponds to between 1000 and 5000 cells per cm².

Freezing protocol:

- After treatment with TrypLE Express, centrifuge at 300 rcf, 5 min, then resuspend in 90% FBS + DMSO 10%
- It is recommended to freeze between 1 and 2 million MSCs/vial (in about 1 mL)!

Figure 1 – Typical morphology of MSCs derived from adipose tissue (fibroblastic-like morphology). Bar, 50 μm